

Tourist Satisfaction and Repeat Visitation; Toward a New Comprehensive Model

Ahmad Puad Mat Som and Mohammad Bader Badarneh

Abstract—Tourism researchers have recently focused on repeat visitation as a part of destination loyalty. Different models have also considered satisfaction as the main determinant of revisit intention, while findings in many studies show it as a continuous issue. This conceptual paper attempts at evaluating recent empirical studies on satisfaction and revisit intention. Based on limitations and gaps in recent studies, the current paper suggests a new model that would be more comprehensive than those in previous studies. The new model offers new relationships between antecedents (destination image, perceived value, specific novelty seeking, and distance to destination) and both of satisfaction and revisit intention. Revisit intention in turn is suggested to be measured in a temporal approach.

Keywords—Satisfaction, revisit intention, a new model

I. INTRODUCTION

TRAVEL and tourism is one of the largest service industries in the world. When tourism is well planned, it can generate benefits at the destination by increasing tourist receipts, government revenue, and employment. For more successful tourism development, it is crucial to attract tourists and to recommend the destination for others to revisit [1]. Recent tourism marketing researches focus mainly on competitiveness, attractiveness, tourist loyalty to a destination, tourist satisfaction and perceived service quality, and destination image [2], [3], [4], [5], [6].

Despite the little attention of repeat visitation, recent studies have begun regarding the important role of revisit of creating more dynamic tourism sector and more distinguished tourist experience [7], [8], [9], [10], [11]. In general, contemporary marketing has discussed repeat purchases as one of the most significant themes by its beneficial rewards such as creating positive word-of-mouth, achieving better cost-effective by repeat visitors, and increasing economic profits [12].

In turn, repeat visitation in tourism is an important phenomenon in the economy as a whole as well as in the individual attraction. Further important role of repeat visitation would be in international tourism flows. The possible explanation to this potential role is that the current visit provokes positively the visitors' likelihood towards an individual repeat visit in some subsequent periods. Indeed, the current visitors may affect also other people's likelihood when

Ahmad Puad Mat Som is a lecturer in tourism at the school of Housing, Building, and Planning, Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM). E-mail: puadusm@gmail.com.

Mohammad Bader Badarneh is a Ph.D. student of tourism planning and development at the school of Housing, Building, and Planning, Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM). E-mail: fuara78@yahoo.com.

they show them their own perception of the visit and their intention for a second visit [13]. Previous researches argued that repeat visitors were more satisfied about the whole trip experience than first timers [11], [14]. In this context, Oppermann [15] confirmed the importance of visitors' past experience for a better detailed demand for level of awareness. Gitelson & Crompton [11] recognized the vital role that repeat vacation plays. They indicated that many attraction areas such as resorts must pay an intense attention to repeat visitation. Thus, this conceptual paper is an attempt to evaluate repeat visitation determinants through satisfaction based on recent previous studies from 2000 until 2010. Clear consensus is demonstrated about a group of determinants of revisit intention. As a continuous theme, limitations and gaps were found of theoretically revisit intention measurement. The current paper therefore reviews these limitations and suggests a new model that would be more comprehensive by showing new relationships between determinants and adding a further determinant. In section two, the paper refers to the importance of satisfaction in repeat visitation and analyzes theoretical studies (between 2000 until 2010) about satisfaction as a mediator between determinants and behavioral intention of tourists. Novelty seeking as an important determinant is discussed in section three. Section four explains the suggested model of the study. And finally the conclusion is included in section five.

II. SATISFACTION AND REPEAT VISITATION

A. Introduction

Previous literatures have discussed factors creating important motivators for tourists' behavior towards a repeat visitation to the same destination. The most undertaken factors have been: visitors' satisfaction and perceived quality [7], [16], safety and risk reduction [9], [11], novelty [8], destination competitiveness [17], and past experience and destination image [3], [9]. However, some of these factors may be applicable separately on first-time visitors, but the whole factors could concern repeaters. As well, among such factors there are the same components of each one but under different names. Yet, the consensus among the researchers confirms the role of satisfaction to be a mediator between some determinants and revisit intention, although they are different in modeling the relationships between all variables in this field.

B. Satisfaction in Tourist's Behavioral Intention

As a whole, customer satisfaction has been considered a

basic business goal due to that the more a customer is satisfied the more he is willing to buy more. Many companies, for that reason, have started to observe a high customer defection even with high satisfaction levels [18], [19]. Satisfaction also has been a central subject of tourist's behaviour. Measuring satisfaction in post-consumption moments aims at providing feedback from a current customer to push managers towards service improvement [20]. This feedback is argued to be an effective way when comparing the performance of one destination with another [21]. Therefore, satisfaction, being positive or negative, can be determined by performance and regarded as a vital basis of competitive issues [22], [23]. Further, it is one of the main success factors of destination marketing regarding its important role in tourists' mind to choose the destination and thereby to probably take a decision to return [4]. Concerning its role in repurchase intention, tourist satisfaction level should be intensively studied for many practical reasons since costumers repurchase intention and loyalty are closely associated with their initial purchase. Its effect on repurchase intention and word-of-mouth (WOM) explains its utmost importance [24], [25].

Customer satisfaction is significant to achieve loyalty not only in physical products [26], [27], but also in tourism context when visitors intend to revisit the same destination [15], [28], or another within the same country [29]. It is generally known in tourism that high quality of service would result in tourist satisfaction, create a positive word-of-mouth, and lead to repeat visits. This in turn affects suppliers' financial performance in tourism industry. Accordingly, most tourism organizers and stakeholders perform regularly tourist satisfaction surveys. The important issue when applying surveys for that purpose is how to use results in policies' implementation [2]. Services in tourism, according to Gronroos [30], take two quality dimensions: the first is technical which concerns what tourists get at the destination. The second is functional referring to the manner they get services. At the destination, product is presented as a bundle of elements such as transportation, accommodation, and entertainment. These can be drawn by the level of tourist satisfaction to each dimension [2].

C. Tourist Satisfaction; an Integral Factor in Revisit

Previous theoretical studies on factors influencing revisit intention have considered tourist satisfaction as a backbone of their models. Despite this common factor among most studies in this field, the way detailing satisfaction and determining its influential factors has been a continuous issue. In their model, Baker and Crompton [31] used both satisfaction and performance quality for revisit intention measurement. They however hypothesized that performance quality has a direct influence on behavioral intentions which are in the model represented by: (1) loyalty to the event (2) and willingness to pay more. It has an indirect influence on them through satisfaction. Omitting the non-recursive relationship between satisfaction and performance quality was justified based on the study findings. Items to affect performance quality in the

model were: (1) generic features (2) specific entertainment features (3) information sources (4) and comfort amenities. Both first and second items had stronger linkage with quality compared to the third and fourth ones. This linkage, argued Baker and Crompton [31], was confirmed by previous studies. Practically, participants' satisfaction in this model was measured globally as far how it was in performance quality. Thus, measuring factors such as performance quality through specific items may develop respondents' perceptions and lead to more meaningful findings.

A comparative empirical study by Kozak [9] was conducted in two destinations in two different countries: Spain and Turkey. The results were described as different between a mature and a less-developed destination. The study used a model that shows how four factors affect the intention to return: satisfaction level, number of past visits to the destination, number of past visits to the country, and other factors such as politic, economic, and temporal. The model proposes that the intention to revisit the same destination is linked with the first three; this linkage is also applied to visit different destinations in the same country. The overall satisfaction in the study treated domains like level of hospitality and customer care, availability of local transportation, and availability of destination airport services. Findings indicated that the more mature is a destination the more repeaters it receives. In addition to the mentioned factors in the study, maturity may include the way in which local people interact with tourists. This factor contributes to influence the level of satisfaction and therefore affects the revisit intention. However, the intention to revisit according to the findings included the same visited destination as well as others in the same country. This finding may lead to that maturity of the destination is excluded when the intention is to revisit the country but to other destination. By this study, determinants like destination competitiveness is important to focus on since tourists intend to revisit a destination due to its maturity.

Akama and Kieti [32] examined tourist satisfaction in a national park in Kenya. Findings showed that participants were mostly satisfied with the destination product. Despite this satisfaction, the yearly park visitors' number is modest. A logical possible explanation may be related to the visited country as a Third World one. Notwithstanding the tourists' satisfaction, the word-of-mouth could be weak or absent. This may lead to another fact that the overall satisfaction is sometimes insufficient for achieving tourists' loyalty. Based on the study conclusion, necessity for further exogenous factors in such a case is understandable to not let tour operators replace the current destination.

An examination of how motivation and satisfaction affect loyalty was modeled by Yoon and Uysal [4]. In the study model, motivation is divided into push factors (internal forces) and pull factors (external forces). Both of them affect destination loyalty. Motivation has two forces: psychological needs and wants. It is therefore a complex proposition to understand why people travel and what they need to enjoy. It

is argued in this study that motivation in behavioral researches needs further domains other than examining tourists' wants and needs. In this context, Swan and Combs [33] pointed out that physical products and psychological interpretation are important for human actions. Based on that, Yoon and Uysal [4] recognized the role of satisfaction for better tourists' loyalty measurement regardless of their expectations. From the study findings, the researchers concluded that internal motives such as relaxation, family togetherness, safety, and fun were significant in participants' responses. These motives in addition to destination attributes represent external sources that create a positive relationship to the destination loyalty. Accordingly, a unique measurement of satisfaction and loyalty has been revealed.

Satisfaction has been an overall perception by being described as: expectation-satisfaction, worth visiting, and comparison with other places. The need here for detailing satisfaction is based on Kozak [29]'s argument that motivations differ from one person to another in the same group, or from one group to another with the same activity. A similar previous study by Kozak [9] referred to the same argument but it concerned satisfaction apart. Nield, Kozak, and LeGrys [34], for example, examined the role of food services in tourist's satisfaction. Such a study ignored the comprehensive overview recommended by latter studies like do Valle, Silva, and Mendes [35]. The study used both structural equation modeling (SEM) and categorical principal components analysis (CATPCA) to explore the relationship between travel satisfaction and destination loyalty. With (SEM) technique they substantiated the importance of satisfaction to determine loyalty, while with (CATPCA) cluster analyses were used. Two clusters were described; the first concerns tourists with high level of satisfaction and willingness to revisit, and the second describes those with low satisfaction level having a weak intention to revisit. By the (CATPCA), the very satisfied tourists are willing to recommend the destination to others and not to return. This study seems to be better than many previous studies due to: (1) the usage of two techniques leading to more precise results (2) describing satisfaction in details under three main sets: general satisfaction, attribute satisfaction, and met expectation. Nevertheless, The study pointed to the need of the following components: (1) considering met expectation in terms of satisfaction of the destination experience on a more detailed scale to achieve a higher loading of the scale (2) through the (SEM), satisfaction contributes to "tourism loyalty" and not to "actual destination loyalty".

Satisfaction and revisit intention alike have been influenced by the perceived attractiveness more than by both perceived quality of services and value for money [36]. Meanwhile, attractiveness (described here as destination performance) was revisit intention determinant more than the overall satisfaction. Nevertheless, for better prediction, stated the authors, attractiveness should be developed due to its positioning in an omnibus way in the model. In addition, the heterogeneous sampling group in the study leads to the

necessity for specific examination of cross-cultural issues. A following study proposed a new model showing how destination image and trip quality affect perceived value, and how these three, in turn, affect satisfaction [1]. It also proposed in the model that satisfaction, both trip quality and perceived value will affect behavioral intention. Satisfaction in this study was grouped with quality and perceived value, while destination image was considered apart and had the most important influence on behavioral intention by influencing not only the decision-making process but also issues after decision-making.

Despite the wide agreement among authors of the role of destination image on process, few empirical researches have been conducted [37]. Moreover in this model, positioning perceived value as a moderator between quality and satisfaction has been neglected in previous research. An indirect effect of trip quality is revealed by the findings which makes subsequently the positive behavioral intention uncertain. The whole results are similar to what found Bigne, Sanchez, and Sanches [38]. Later, Hui, Wan, and Ho [7] have developed a model for measuring tourist satisfaction. In their model they explain the dependence of customer's repeat purchase and loyalty on his or her satisfaction. They also refer to the influence of satisfaction on the word-of-mouth. The study has been conducted on tourists departing from "Changi International Airport" in Singapore. The main findings in the study confirmed the likelihood of respondents to recommend Singapore to their friends and families. Their overall satisfaction from the visit was the determinant of this likelihood. This satisfaction affected respondents positively to revisit the country. On the other side, many tourists responded negatively regarding a potential revisiting, they were more likely to spread the positive word of mouth than to return due mainly to the small geographical size of Singapore which is easily to be accomplished in few days. Expectations and experiences are determinants to affect disconfirmation in the model; experiences with disconfirmation will affect directly the overall satisfaction which will affect finally destination loyalty. It is recommended in the study that confidence in expectations could be a moderator between expectations and perceptions. This is based on previous studies which indicate that high confidence in expectations forms senses of satisfaction through disconfirmation and perceptions, and through perceptions only for low confidence.

Revisit intention measurement with respect to its temporal change is a new perspective in a new study [8]. They justify the importance of this usage that revisit intention usually changes over time. Hence, novelty seeking and destination satisfaction have been modeled to influence short-term (within twelve months), mid-term (within three years), and long-term (within five years) revisit intention. Satisfaction affected positively the short-term revisit intention. Meanwhile, the effect of novelty was positive but in the mid-term. The researchers recommended the development of a comprehensive temporal model by adding further determinants mentioned in previous research even with

different context. Satisfaction could be represented as post-trip evaluation by both repeaters and first-timers [39]. Comparing first and repeat visitors in this study is significant to recognize their characteristics and to contribute to methodology in the field. The way in which first-timers and repeaters evaluate pre- and post-trip should be present. This to be achievable, it is necessary to find out that first time visitors were more active than repeaters (who were more positive evaluators). Unwariness of respondents' travel history was a limitation of this study since repeaters' satisfaction is more likely to be stable than in the case of first-timers based on their length travel history. The fact that those with first time visit to the current destination does not mean that their travel experience is modest; this may make a further limitation.

Chi and Qu [40] offered an integrated approach to understand destination loyalty and satisfaction as determined by destination image and attribute. The results confirmed the significant overall satisfaction effect on destination loyalty, as well as the two mentioned determinants on the overall satisfaction. Destination image in turn was found to affect significantly tourist satisfaction. A series of competing models was analyzed in order to reveal alternative explanations to the main proposed model in this study. Indeed, such models have not diversity in basic components in similar models but they added paths between them and destination loyalty.

As in the above mentioned studies, overall satisfaction and loyalty were measured by just a single question, the research therefore suggests a multiple-item scale to measure for example the temporal repurchase intention as offered in Jang and Feng [8]'s study. As well, satisfaction (determined by destination image) and perceived value was examined to affect revisit intention [41]. The study model shows also how past switching behavior, switching cost, and specific variety seeking affect separately and directly revisit intention. Findings of the study did not show significant effect of satisfaction and its determinants in the model, while the rest of antecedents had significant effect. They however had long-term and short-term effects of return intention. Considering the temporal intention and focusing on specific novelty seeking were a contribution of this study, while the way in which return intention was examined reflects most previous studies' models.

A recent study by Zabkar, Brenc, and Dmitrovic [2] explored the complex relationship between main constructs and behavioral intention modeled as: destination attributes affect perceived quality which then affects satisfaction. In turn, perceived quality and satisfaction affect revisit intention. Although its results confirmed this complex relationship, the study recommends to future studies to test the universality of such a model apart from (destination-specific) attributes set used as indicators for the perceived quality. Perceived value, e.g., could be a mediator in the model between perceived quality and behavioral intention. Other constructs such as price, risk perception, and destination image could be also included. Such recommendations have been taken into considerations when Assaker, Vinzi, and O'Connor [42]

hypothesized causal relationships between different variables as: destination image determines satisfaction which subsequently affects both initial status and shape factor as well does novelty separately. Jang and Feng [8] measured the temporal visit retention revealing that satisfaction influenced retention to visit in the short term. The researchers pointed to a limitation of using a single measurement item for satisfaction and image in the study. Multiple dimensions could be better for more robust findings and to avoid measurement errors. Novelty seeking was demonstrated in the findings to have negative effects on immediate revisit and positive on revisit intention in the future. Yet, effects of this antecedent had discrepancies comparing with other studies [8], [41]. However, the continuous role of novelty seeking would be beneficial in the arena.

III. NOVELTY SEEKING

Novelty seeking is a fundamental component for travel motivation. It is defined as the level of contrast between current perception and past experience [43]. It also refers to a behavioral curiosity, an exploratory drive, and sensation seeking [44]. In travel and tourism, novelty seeking is the level of contrast between current perception and past experience. It makes the opposite of familiarity [8]. Crofts [45] investigated the importance of novelty in tourism as an enhancer for tourist's satisfaction. Novelty has been widely asserted, as referred Petrick [46], to play a role in tourists' decision making when choosing their preferable destination. Shoemaker and Lewis [12] indicated that tourists may be satisfied with their hotel but their interest changes negatively their loyalty level. Indeed, novelty measurement in tourism is complicated. Bello and Etzel [47] defined it as trip with unfamiliar experience. Basically, they proposed three elements that describe novelty: (1) the one's preference to a special level of stimulation (2) the need to novelty, adventure, and other factors when the level of stimulation is not optimal (3) when stimulation is greater than the optimal level, the organism will seek for manners to reduce it. In their three propositions for novelty, Bello and Etzel [47] agreed with Berlyne [48] since he found out that rational level of novelty is preferred, while its extreme level inhibits visitors' exploratory behavior. According to Zuckerman [49], novelty is likely to be related to the level of arousal that they desire. He argued that the amount of arousal differs genetically from tourist to another. Tourists therefore will have different degree of novelty although they are in the same tourist activity.

Accordingly, Mehrabian and Russell [50] in their 'arousal seeking scale' determined factors such as risk, sensuality, and new environment. Such factors thus may find the different measurement of tourists within the same activity. Petrick [46] pointed to the degree of novelty according to types of tourists. He argued that organized mass tourists depend highly on their "environmental bubble" and that their choice for a destination is dominated by familiarity. The same behavior for individual mass tourists is described although they tend to be free from

groups. He also referred to that explorers (described as being more independent from the “environmental bubble” than the previous types) are more likely to have extraordinary experience and to interact with local people.

Little attention has been paid by the research to the role of variety or novelty seeking in consumers’ repurchases intention especially in services [41]. Yet, regarding its relationship with repeat visitation, novelty seeking has been argued to have positive effect [8], [41], [42]. Feng and Jang [51] indicated that continuous repeaters could be comparable to lower novelty-seeking tourists while deferred repeaters represent tourists with at a mid-range level of arousal. The study of Jang and Feng [8] revealed a new function of novelty in reinforcing revisit intention. They however ruled out any relationship between short-term revisit intention and novelty seeking. Main subjects of novelty were about a different culture, original issues related to local people, and variety of the overall sought activities.

A result that novelty seeking has had more significant effect on return intention than satisfaction was pointed out [41]. Focusing on a specific product when measuring the effect of variety may explain this successful relationship. As it was detailed by Jang and Feng [8], novelty was examined with a general perspective [42]. Assaker, Vinzi, and O’Connor [42] pointed out that novelty affect positively revisit intention directly and indirectly (through satisfaction). This refers also to the role that novelty plays in satisfaction. Conversely, some studies posited negative relationship between novelty seeking and return intention [52], [53], [54]. Niininen, Szivas, and Riley [54] examined the role of novelty in destination choice. Various types of destination choice were shown by those with high novelty seeking propensity. Nevertheless, the small sample size in this study may decrease the validity of this result. Berne, Mugica, and Rivera [53] referred also to a negative direct influence of novelty seeking on grocery retailing consumers’ behavioural intention. This field would not reflect the issue with travellers. Barroso, Martin, and Martin [52] proposed a mediator role of novelty seeking tendency and its effect on perceived quality, satisfaction, and return intention. Respondents were segmented according to their level of novelty they seek as well as the way in which they perceive it. They supported the effect of novelty as a moderator by that all variables depend on tourists’ tendency to seek novelty. Though, such results could change depending on some continuous issues such as the way in which novelty is undertaken, the type of products, negative perceptions to one of the journey activities, and some demographic factors. This would lead to further determinants of revisit intention in order to achieve more comprehensive measurement.

IV. NEW SUGGESTED MODEL

Based on the mentioned above theoretical studies, satisfaction is a basic actor in tourists’ behavioural intentions. However, modelling satisfaction is a continuous issue. By them, antecedents of satisfaction without affecting directly

(according to how they are modelled and not to results) the intention to return were: perceived quality [31], [32], [55], expectations and experience perception [7], [35], destination image [40], [42], and destination attributes [2], [32], [40]. On the other hand, many antecedents of satisfaction would lead to the same meaning or concepts but with different words. For example, push motivations play a determinant role of satisfaction [4] that would refer to the destination image since this latter could be defined as the tourists’ subjective perception of the destination reality [1].

Further, pull motivations [4] would lead to the same destination attributes’ components and perceived quality since pull motivations concern an overall product. Similarly, within pull and push motivations; exogenous factors such as natural environment and endogenous factors such as accommodation are components of the destination image [40], and it would consequently comprise perceived quality. Once again, destination image is a determinant to affect both satisfaction and revisit intention as it is modelled by Bigne, Sanchez, and Andreu [41] contrary to what Assaker Vinzi, and O’Connor [42] and Chi and Qu [40] have done. The existence of destination image thus could be beneficial because of its significant effect on satisfaction and revisit intention as a comprehensive determinant. Perceived value is an antecedent to affect satisfaction and revisit intention each apart [1], [41]. It is the tourists’ evaluation of the net worth of the trip based on benefits (what is received) and cost (what is given) [1]. It may be argued therefore that the perceived money value would determine tourists’ image.

According to the limitations in the earlier studies, the need for additional determinants could lead to better measurement. This point of view was implicitly confirmed by Gitelson and Crompton [11] when they found that many satisfied respondents did not intend to return because they seek for new experience in their future potential trip.

Hence, this paper suggests novelty seeking to be a determinant of revisit intention, due to that few studies focused on it [41]. They also argued that specific novelty seeking in a concrete product category could enrich respondents’ propensity. To contribute to the way it affects intention to revisit, the current suggested model would undertake novelty to affect directly satisfaction and once again directly revisit intention. Based on Assaker, Vinzi, and O’Connor [42], novelty was significant to affect destination image and then revisit intention. Thus, the justification of its effect on satisfaction in the current suggested model is that destination image was revealed to affect significantly satisfaction [1], [41], [42], [43]. These studies, excepting Assaker, Vinzi, and O’Connor [42], have undertaken novelty to affect only and directly revisit intention. Accordingly, the following relationships in the suggested model could be argued: (1) destination image would affect both satisfaction and revisit intention (2) perceived value would affect destination image, satisfaction, and revisit intention (3) and novelty would affect both satisfaction and revisit intention.

Furthermore, this paper proposes distance as determinant of

V. CONCLUSION

perceived value and revisit intention. The research in this context did not show it in such a relationship, while it was used to determine travel motivations and destination choice [56], [57], [58]. Distance or geographical situation of tourists relative to destinations is a restriction of destination choice due to temporal and monetary causes [59], [60]. Alternatively, it can be useful and positive for choosing a destination. Long distance increases satisfaction of the whole journey [61], [62]. Therefore, the absence of a consensus regarding the role of distance on destination choice would be the same when it concerns the return intention. Nicolau and Mas [56] found out that distance is a dissuasive element of destination choice. They however showed the relationship between distance and both of travel motivation and choice. In view of that, the current suggested model would propose a relationship between distance and perceived value as well as revisit intention.

Regarding revisit intention, it is shown in the model as a part of loyalty. Indeed, loyalty can lead to revisit intention and likelihood to recommend the visited destination. Hence, focusing on revisit intention may make respondents more specific when expressing their sensation to the destination. Hui, Wan, and Ho [7] revealed that tourists who were satisfied from the whole trip were likely to recommend the destination to others rather than to revisit it in the future. Oppermann [10] and Oppermann [63] found that less satisfied visitors might revisit the same destination. Therefore, asking tourists only about their intention to return would refer implicitly to their willingness to recommend it. In addition, measuring the temporal revisit intention should be more beneficial than being in general. It leads therefore to more specific responses of revisit intention and more clarification for satisfaction level [8], [41], [42].

Figure. 1 represents a new suggested model that would be more comprehensive than those in previous studies.

Fig. 1 A suggested model of revisit intention

Over the past two decades, several researches attempted to find out reasons behind tourists' return intention to the destination. Satisfaction as modeled in most of these researches has had significant relationship with repeat visitation intention. According to Yi [64], satisfaction is a mediator of attitude changes since it is considered as a psychological state. Yet, limitations and gaps revealed by them lead to that satisfaction, even with further antecedents, is still a continuous research. Based on limitations and gaps of recent studies, the current paper suggests new relationships and antecedents to have significant effects on revisit intention. Hence, the following main discussions would contribute to the field:

Suggesting new relationships among satisfaction and other antecedents to be influential on revisit intention; destination image may have logical influence on satisfaction and revisit intention apart. Such a relationship could be imposed due to that destination image comprises some antecedents which had the similar effect such as push and pull factors [4], [40], perceived quality [31], [32], and destination attributes [2], [32], [40]. Plus, perceived value may have significant effect on destination image since it comprises, according to Bigne, Sanchez, and Andreu [41], Chen and Tsai [1], Um, Chon, and Ro [36], the tourists' evaluation of the trip based on the benefit and cost. Another new suggested relationship in the current study is the direct effect of novelty on satisfaction that had significance on destination image [42], while in other studies it had only effect on revisit intention [1], [40], [41], [42].

Specifying novelty rather than undertaking it in a general perspective; this can be justified based on previous studies which show that satisfied tourists had no intention to revisit the same destination in the future [7], [11]. Specific novelty would be the reason of repeat visitation, although it did not gain researchers' attention [41].

Adding a further factor to be a main antecedent of satisfaction and then revisit intention; since distance to destination is related to temporal and monetary issues [59], [60], it can influence the whole perceived value and revisit intention. Perceived value in turn was described to be related to monetary (price) and nonmonetary (time, search costs, convenience) evaluation [65]. The existence of this variable is suggested in the current paper not only because of its relation to the perceived value, it is also a response of previous studies' recommendations for using additional determinants of repeat visitation [7], [32].

Focusing only on revisit intention rather than loyalty; this way would reveal to more precise responses regarding the intention to return. Those with revisit intention are logically willing to recommend the current destination (they are loyal in all senses), while those who are willing to recommend the destination may not return [7], [10], [63].

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